

Analysis of Slit Curvature Using Image Processing

Atomic Spectroscopy Laboratory¹

¹Física Teórica, Atómica y Óptica, Universidad de Valladolid,

P.º de Belén, 7, Valladolid, 47011, Spain

`astrolab.dpto.ftao@uva.es`

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Abstract

This report presents an experiment aimed at determining the parameters for the curvature of a monochromator's entrance slit. The experiment involves fitting parabolas and circles to images of the entrance slit of the monochromator obtained from a CMOS detector when a LASER (632.8 nm) is placed in front of it. The results ensure accurate wavelength calibration and precise spectral measurements in future spectroscopic studies.

1 Introduction

Extracting a spectrum from the camera-captured image in spectroscopic experiments is essential for accurate wavelength measurements. After an image is acquired with the detector/camera, a one-dimensional spectrum (intensity versus wavelength) is typically obtained by adding the intensity of all the pixels in the same column. However, the image of the spectrometer's entrance slit is not perfectly rectangular but curved to reduce geometric aberrations, not chromatic aberrations as is sometimes incorrectly assumed. The curvature of the entrance slit ensures that all points forming the slit are at approximately the same distance from the optical axis, equalising geometric aberrations for all points of the slit. This report presents an experiment to determine the parameters of the curvature using parabolic and circular models to correct for the slit's curvature and ensure accurate wavelength calibration and precise spectral measurements.

2 Why is the Slit Curved?

The curvature of the entrance slit in a spectrometer, such as the Czerny-Turner setup used in this experiment, is implemented to reduce geometric aberrations rather than chromatic aberrations. The following explanation details the reasons for this curvature:

2.1 Chromatic Aberration

Both magnification chromatic aberration and positional chromatic aberration are caused by the dispersion of optical glasses (the variation of the refractive index with wavelength). However, in a Czerny-Turner spectrometer, the image-forming systems are mirrors, which

are free from dispersion and, consequently, from chromatic aberrations. Although the diffraction grating has a strongly dispersive behavior, as an image-forming system, it behaves like a flat mirror and is free from chromatic aberrations.

Even if some dispersive element were present, the narrow range of wavelengths used in a spectrometer would make chromatic aberrations practically undetectable in the output spectra.

2.2 Purpose of Slit Curvature

The real reason for the curvature of the entrance slit is to ensure that all points on the slit are approximately equidistant from the optical axis of the spectrometer. This design minimizes the variation in aberrations across the slit, ensuring that the quality of the image formed from different parts of the slit is similar. It does not mean that the aberrations are eliminated, but rather that they are consistent across the entire slit.

In practice, the slit is designed to follow a circular segment or arc, with the center of the arc located on the optical axis. This arc is perpendicular to the meridional plane, and only the center of the slit lies within the meridional plane.

2.3 Geometric Aberrations in Czerny-Turner Spectrometers

A Czerny-Turner spectrometer is a symmetric optical system, which means that odd aberrations, such as coma and distortion, are null due to symmetry. However, even aberrations, such as spherical aberration, astigmatism, and curvature of field, are present, and various strategies are used to minimize them.

- **Spherical Aberration:** This is reduced by using parabolic mirrors instead of spherical mirrors. While spherical aberration would be zero if the object were on the optical axis, the points of the slit are near the axis, making spherical aberration small but not completely negligible.
- **Astigmatism:** Astigmatism arises from the distance between sagittal and tangential focal points. The configuration of the system must be optimized to minimize its effects. Sagittal focal points are found in planes perpendicular to the meridional plane, while tangential focal points lie parallel to the meridional plane.
- **Curvature of Field:** Sagittal curvature is zero due to the system's symmetry, and all sagittal focal points are located in the paraxial image plane, forming small segments. Since the points forming the slit are perpendicular to the meridional plane, the image of the slit becomes broader, which is undesirable.

To minimize this broadening, the detector is typically placed in the plane where the tangential focal points are located, preventing the width of the slit image from increasing unnecessarily.

3 Experimental Setup

The experimental setup integrates three essential components: a He-Ne LASER, a 1.5 m Jobin-Yvon Czerny-Turner spectrometer with reflective diffraction grating of 2400 lines/mm, resolving power of 150,000 at 450 nm, and a spectral range from 200 nm to

800 nm, and a CMOS PCO Edge 4.2 UV camera featuring high sensitivity, a pixel size of $6.5 \mu m$, and a quantum efficiency of up to 95% at 600 nm. The camera is used to capture images of spectral lines formed at the monochromator's exit plane, which are then processed to extract the curvature of the entrance slit.

The 632.8 nm LASER line is captured using the detector's app and saved. The monochromator tuning was changed by 0.1 nm each time to capture the spectral line at different detector points. The captured images of the entrance slit to varying tunings of the monochromator are shown in Figure 1 All the captured images were saved. These saved images will be used in the following sections of the code.

Figure 1: Image of entrance slit captured by the detector for different tunings of the monochromator. The red line on each entrance slit image denotes the maxima determined by the MATLAB function *find_row_maxima*. These points will be used to fit the slit images with circular or parabolic models in the subsequent sections.

4 Fitting Circles

The slit curvature was modeled using a circular fit. The circular function was fitted to the maxima found in the captured images, and the corresponding parameters were extracted. The fitting was done using a least-squares method, and the goodness of the fit was evaluated by calculating the RMSE (denoted as σ). The lower the σ , the better the fit.

The following MATLAB function allows users to obtain circular parameters from multiple selected images:

Listing 1: Circle Parameters Extraction

```
function obtain_circle_parameters()
% Function to obtain circular parameters from multiple
% selected images
% User selects multiple images and provides a region of
% interest (ROI)
% The function fits circular arcs to the maxima of the images
% and saves the parameters

clc;

% Allow user to select multiple images
[image_files, image_path] = uigetfile('*.tif', 'Select .tiff
Images', 'MultiSelect', 'on');
if isequal(image_files, 0)
    disp('User canceled image selection. ');
    return;
end

% Convert single selection to a cell array for consistency
if ischar(image_files)
    image_files = {image_files};
end

% Get region of interest (ROI) from the user
prompt = {'Enter lower Y limit (ylower):', 'Enter upper Y
limit (yupper):'};
dlgtitle = 'ROI Input';
dims = [1 35];
definput = {'41', '2000'}; % Default values, can be adjusted
roi = inputdlg(prompt, dlgtitle, dims, definput);

if isempty(roi)
    disp('User canceled ROI input. ');
    return;
end

% Parse ROI values
ylower = str2double(roi{1});
yupper = str2double(roi{2});

% Initialize arrays for storing results
num_images = length(image_files);
all_maxima = [];

% Loop through all selected images
for i = 1:num_images
    % Load image
```

```

image = imread(fullfile(image_path, image_files{i}));
[ul_row, ul_col] = size(image); % Get the dimensions of
    the image

% Ensure ROI is within image boundaries
if yupper > ul_row
    yupper = ul_row;
end

% Find row maxima in the image
maxima = find_row_maxima(image);
all_maxima = [all_maxima; maxima]; % Append maxima from
    each image
end

% Plot the summed maxima overlaid on an empty image
figure;
imshow(zeros(ul_row, ul_col), []); hold on;
plot(all_maxima(:,2), all_maxima(:,1), 'ro', 'MarkerSize', 2)
    ; % Observed maxima

% Preallocate for theoretical maxima and fitted parameters
rr = zeros(num_images, 1); % Radius of the circle
xxv = zeros(num_images, 1); % X center of the circle
yyv = zeros(num_images, 1); % Y center of the circle
sigma=zeros(1,num_images);

% Define anonymous function for circle fitting
circleFit = @(params, x, y) sqrt((x - params(1)).^2 + (y -
    params(2)).^2) - params(3);

% Fit each image's maxima to the circular model
for ii = 1:num_images
    idx_start = (ii-1)*ul_row + 1;
    idx_end = ii*ul_row;

    % Ensure the indices don't exceed the available data
    if idx_end > size(all_maxima, 1)
        idx_end = size(all_maxima, 1);
    end

    idx = idx_start:idx_end;
    x = all_maxima(idx, 2); % Maxima column indices
    y = all_maxima(idx, 1); % Row indices

    % Use the region of interest (ROI) for fitting
    if length(y) > yupper
        x = x(ylower:yupper);
        y = y(ylower:yupper);
    end
end

```

```

% Initial guess for [x_center, y_center, radius]
initial_guess = [mean(x), mean(y), range(x)/2];

% Perform non-linear least squares fit
options = optimset('Display', 'off');
fit_params = lsqnonlin(@(params) circleFit(params, x, y),
    initial_guess, [], [], options);

% Store fitted parameters
xxv(ii) = fit_params(1);
yyv(ii) = fit_params(2);
rr(ii) = fit_params(3);

% Generate theoretical maxima based on the fit, only for
ROI
theta = linspace(0, 2*pi, 100);
theoretical_maxima_x = xxv(ii) + rr(ii) * cos(theta);
theoretical_maxima_y = yyv(ii) + rr(ii) * sin(theta);

% Plot fitted circular arc
plot(theoretical_maxima_x, theoretical_maxima_y, 'b-', '
    LineWidth', 1.5);

% Calculate RMSE for the fit
sigma(ii) = sqrt(mean((circleFit(fit_params, x, y)).^2));
end

legend('Observed_Maxima', 'Fitted_Circle', 'Location', 'Best'
);
hold off;

% Polynomial fit for xxv and yyv (X and Y center coordinates)
. The centres lie on a straight line with a slope which is
equal to the angle between the optical axis of the
monochromator and the center of the detector
figure;
[xData, yData] = prepareCurveData(xxv, yyv);
[fitresult, gof] = fit(xData, yData, 'poly1');

% Plot polynomial fit result
h = plot(fitresult, xData, yData);
m=fitresult.p1;
c=fitresult.p2;
grid on;
set(gca, 'FontSize', 14, 'LineWidth', 1.5, 'GridLineStyle', '
--');
xlabel('X_Center_(units)', 'FontSize', 16, 'FontWeight', '
bold');
ylabel('Y_Center_(units)', 'FontSize', 16, 'FontWeight', '
bold');
title('Fitted_Linear_Model_for_Circle_Centers', 'FontSize',

```

```

    18, 'FontWeight', 'bold');
legend(h, {'Fitted Line', 'Data Points'}, 'Location', 'best',
       'FontSize', 14);

% Add R^2 value to the plot
annotation('textbox', [0.15, 0.75, 0.2, 0.1], 'String',
          sprintf('R^2 = %.4f', gof.rsquare), ...
          'FitBoxToText', 'on', 'FontSize', 14, 'BackgroundColor',
          'white', 'EdgeColor', 'black');

% Save circle parameters to a .mat file
rr=mean(rr);
save('circle_parameters.mat', 'rr', 'm', 'c');
plot(sigma)
legend('Parabolic', 'Circular')
end

% Helper function to find row maxima
function maxima = find_row_maxima(image)
    [~, max_idx] = max(image, [], 2); % Get column indices of max
    value in each row
    maxima = [(1:size(image, 1))', max_idx]; % [Row index, Max
    column index]
end

```

How to Use the Function

1. Copy the provided 'obtain_circle_parameters' function into a MATLAB script.
2. Run the script in MATLAB.
3. A file selection dialog will appear; select multiple '.tif' images containing the entrance slit data. Please select all the images captured using the detector and its app.
4. Input the region of interest (ROI) by providing the lower and upper Y limits when prompted.
5. The function will fit circles to the maxima of the selected images and display the observed and fitted curves.
6. The fitted parameters will be saved in 'circle_parameters.mat'.

5 Fitting Parabolas

The slit curvature was also modeled using a parabolic fit. Similar to the circular fit, the parabola was fitted to the row maxima found in the images. The parameters of the parabola were extracted, and the goodness of fit was evaluated using RMSE.

The MATLAB function provided below enables users to extract parabolic parameters from selected images:

Listing 2: Parabola Parameters Extraction

```

function obtain_parabola_parameters()
    % Function to obtain parabolic parameters from multiple
    selected images

```

```

% User selects multiple images and provides a region of
  interest (ROI)
% The function fits parabolic curves to the maxima of the
  images and saves the parameters

clc;

% Allow user to select multiple images
[image_files, image_path] = uigetfile('*.tif', 'Select .tiff
  Images', 'MultiSelect', 'on');
if isequal(image_files, 0)
    disp('User canceled image selection. ');
    return;
end

% Convert single selection to a cell array for consistency
if ischar(image_files)
    image_files = {image_files};
end

% Get region of interest (ROI) from the user
prompt = {'Enter lower Y limit (ylower):', 'Enter upper Y
  limit (yupper):'};
dlgtitle = 'ROI Input';
dims = [1 35];
definput = {'41', '2000'}; % Default values, can be adjusted
roi = inputdlg(prompt, dlgtitle, dims, definput);

if isempty(roi)
    disp('User canceled ROI input. ');
    return;
end

% Parse ROI values
ylower = str2double(roi{1});
yupper = str2double(roi{2});

% Initialize arrays for storing results
num_images = length(image_files);
all_maxima = [];

% Loop through all selected images
for i = 1:num_images
    % Load image
    image = imread(fullfile(image_path, image_files{i}));
    [ul_row, ul_col] = size(image); % Get the dimensions of
    the image

    % Ensure ROI is within image boundaries
    if yupper > ul_row
        yupper = ul_row;
    end
end

```

```

end

% Find row maxima in the image
maxima = find_row_maxima(image);
all_maxima = [all_maxima; maxima]; % Append maxima from
    each image
end

% Plot the summed maxima overlaid on an empty image
figure;
imshow(zeros(ul_row, ul_col), []); hold on;
plot(all_maxima(:,2), all_maxima(:,1), 'ro', 'MarkerSize', 2)
    ; % Observed maxima

% Preallocate for theoretical maxima and fitted parameters
aa = zeros(num_images, 1); % Parabolic parameter (a)
xxv = zeros(num_images, 1); % X vertex
yyv = zeros(num_images, 1); % Y vertex
sigma=zeros(1,num_images);
% Define fit type and options for fitting parabolic curves
ft = fittype('xv-ua*(x-yv).^2', 'independent', 'x', '
    dependent', 'y');
opts = fitoptions('Method', 'NonlinearLeastSquares', 'Display
    ', 'Off', 'Lower', [0, -Inf, -Inf]);

% Fit each image's maxima to the parabola model
for ii = 1:num_images
    idx_start = (ii-1)*ul_row + 1;
    idx_end = ii*ul_row;

    % Ensure the indices don't exceed the available data
    if idx_end > size(all_maxima, 1)
        idx_end = size(all_maxima, 1);
    end

    idx = idx_start:idx_end;
    y = all_maxima(idx, 2); % Maxima row indices
    xx = all_maxima(idx, 1); % column indices

    % Use the region of interest (ROI) for fitting
    if length(xx) > yupper
        y = y(ylower:yupper);
        xx = xx(ylower:yupper);
    end

    [xData, yData] = prepareCurveData(xx, y);

    % Fit the parabola model
    [fitresult, gof] = fit(xData, yData, ft, opts);

    % Store fitted parameters

```

```

aa(ii) = fitresult.a;
xxv(ii) = fitresult.xv;
yyv(ii) = fitresult.yv;

% Generate theoretical maxima based on the fit, only for
ROI
theoretical_maxima = fitresult.xv - fitresult.a * (xx -
fitresult.yv).^2;

% Plot fitted curve
plot(real(theoretical_maxima), xx, 'b-', 'LineWidth',
1.5);
sigma(ii)=gof.rmse;
end

legend('Observed_Maxima', 'Fitted_Curve', 'Location', 'Best')
;
hold off;

% Polynomial fit for xxv and yyv (X and Y center coordinates)
. The centres lie on a straight line with a slope that is
equal to the angle between the optical axis of the
monochromator and the center of the detector
figure;
[xData, yData] = prepareCurveData(xxv, yyv);
[fitresult, gof] = fit(xData, yData, 'poly1');

% Plot polynomial fit result
h = plot(fitresult, xData, yData);
grid on;
set(gca, 'FontSize', 14, 'LineWidth', 1.5, 'GridLineStyle', '
--');
xlabel('X_Vertex_(units)', 'FontSize', 16, 'FontWeight', '
bold');
ylabel('Y_Vertex_(units)', 'FontSize', 16, 'FontWeight', '
bold');
title('Fitted_Linear_Model_for_Vertex_Parameters', 'FontSize'
, 18, 'FontWeight', 'bold');
legend(h, {'Fitted_Line', 'Data_Points'}, 'Location', 'best',
'FontSize', 14);

% Add R^2 value to the plot
annotation('textbox', [0.15, 0.75, 0.2, 0.1], 'String',
sprintf('R^2= %.4f', gof.rsquare), ...
'FitBoxToText', 'on', 'FontSize', 14, 'BackgroundColor',
'white', 'EdgeColor', 'black');
% set(gcf, 'Position', get(0, 'Screensize')); % Make the
figure full screen

% Calculate final parabola parameters
m = fitresult.p1;

```

```

c = fitresult.p2; % Adjust intercept by ylower
a = mean(aa);

% Save parameters to a .mat file
save('parabola_parameters.mat', 'a', 'c', 'm');
figure
plot(sigma)
end

% Helper function to find row maxima
function maxima = find_row_maxima(image)
    [~, max_idx] = max(image, [], 2); % Get column indices of max
    value in each row
    maxima = [(1:size(image, 1))', max_idx]; % [Row index, Max
    column index]
end

```

How to Use the Function

1. Copy the provided 'obtain_parabola_parameters' function into a MATLAB script.
2. Run the script in MATLAB.
3. A file selection dialog will appear; select multiple '.tif' images containing the entrance slit data. Select all the images captured using the detector and its app.
4. Input the region of interest (ROI) by providing the lower and upper Y limits when prompted.
5. The function will fit parabolas to the maxima of the selected images and display the observed and fitted curves.
6. The fitted parameters will be saved in 'parabola_parameters.mat'.

6 MATLAB Implementation

To automate the calculation of spectra based on parabolic and circular fits, we developed MATLAB scripts. These scripts compute the spectra using circular, parabolic, and linear models and then compare their performance.

6.1 Circular Spectrum Calculation

The circular model computes the spectra along a circular path for each column of the image. This is useful for analyzing images that have circular patterns or regions of interest.

Listing 3: Circular Spectrum Calculation

```

function spect_cur = calculate_circular_spectra(img, roi)
    % Function to calculate the circular spectra from a given
    % image or a specified region of interest (ROI).
    % img - the input image (whole image is considered if ROI is
    % not provided)
    % roi - a 4-element vector [ylower, yupper, xlower, xupper]
    % specifying the region of interest (ROI)

```

```

% Circle parameters (example values, adjust as needed)
load circle_parameters.mat
% Determine the region of interest (ROI)
if nargin < 2 % If ROI is not provided, use the entire image
    [ylower, yupper] = deal(1, size(img, 1)); % Full image
        in Y dimension
    [xlower, xupper] = deal(1, size(img, 2)); % Full image
        in X dimension
else
    ylower = roi(1);
    yupper = roi(2);
    xlower = roi(3);
    xupper = roi(4);
end

% Get the size of the region of interest
ul_row = yupper - ylower + 1;
ul_col = xupper - xlower + 1;

% Initialize the array for the circular spectrum
spect_cur = zeros(1, ul_col); % Circular spectrum

% Loop through each column (channel) within the ROI
for channel = xlower:xupper
    sum_cur = 0;

    % Calculate the Y-coordinate based on the circle model
    for row = ylower:yupper
        % Compute the X-coordinate using the circle equation:
            (x - xc)^2 + (y - yc)^2 = r^2
        xc=channel-rr;
        yc = m * xc + c;

        % yc=m.*xc+c;
        x = xc + sqrt(rr^2 - (row - yc).^2);

        % Only calculate the curved spectrum if x >= 1
        if x >= 1
            if x > ul_col
                sum_cur = sum_cur + double(img(row, ul_col));
                % Use the last column if x exceeds image
                bounds
            else
                col = floor(x); % Integer part of x
                frac = x - col; % Fractional part of x
                sum_cur = sum_cur + double(img(row, col)) *
                    (1 - frac) + double(img(row, col + 1)) *
                    frac;
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

        end
    end

    % Store the average value for the current channel in the
    % spectrum
    spect_cur(channel - xlower + 1) = sum_cur / ul_row;
end
end
end

```

6.2 Parabolic Spectrum Calculation

The parabolic model calculates the spectrum assuming a parabolic path.

Listing 4: Parabolic Spectrum Calculation

```

function spect_cur = calculate_parabolic_spectra(img, roi)
% Function to calculate the parabolic spectra from a given
% image or a specified region of interest (ROI).
% img - the input image (whole image is considered if ROI is
% not provided)
% roi - a 4-element vector [ylower, yupper, xlower, xupper]
% specifying the region of interest (ROI)

% Parabola parameters
load parabola_parameters.mat
% Determine the region of interest (ROI)
if nargin < 2 % If ROI is not provided, use the entire image
    [ylower, yupper] = deal(1, size(img, 1)); % Full image
    % in Y dimension
    [xlower, xupper] = deal(1, size(img, 2)); % Full image
    % in X dimension
else
    ylower = roi(1);
    yupper = roi(2);
    xlower = roi(3);
    xupper = roi(4);
end

% Get the size of the region of interest
ul_row = yupper - ylower + 1;
ul_col = xupper - xlower + 1;

% Initialize the array for the parabolic spectrum
spect_cur = zeros(1, ul_col); % Parabolic spectrum

% Loop through each column (channel) within the ROI
for channel = xlower:xupper
    sum_cur = 0;

    % Calculate the vertex y-coordinate for the current
    % channel
    yv = m * channel + c;

```

```

% Loop through each row within the ROI
for row = ylower:yupper
    % Compute x-coordinate based on the parabola model
    x = channel - a * (row - yv)^2;

    % Only calculate the curved spectrum if x >= 1
    if x >= 1
        if x > ul_col
            sum_cur = sum_cur + double(img(row, ul_col));
            % Use the last column if x exceeds image
            bounds
        else
            col = floor(x); % Integer part of x
            frac = x - col; % Fractional part of x
            sum_cur = sum_cur + double(img(row, col)) *
                (1 - frac) + double(img(row, col + 1)) *
                frac;
        end
    end
end

% Store the average value for the current channel in the
% spectrum
spect_cur(channel - xlower + 1) = sum_cur / ul_row;
end
end

```

6.3 Comparison of Models

The following MATLAB script compares the spectra obtained using circular, parabolic, and linear models.

Listing 5: Spectra Comparison Code

```

% Allow selection of multiple images
[files, path] = uigetfile('*.tif', 'Select Images', 'MultiSelect',
    , 'on');

if ischar(files)
    files = {files};
end

for i = 1:length(files)
    img = imread(fullfile(path, files{i}));
    [ul_row, ul_col] = size(img);

    % Linear spectrum
    spect_lin = zeros(1, ul_col);
    for channel = 1:ul_col
        sum_lin = 0;
    end
end

```

```

    for row = 1:ul_row
        sum_lin = sum_lin + double(img(row, channel));
    end
    spect_lin(channel) = sum_lin / ul_row;
end

% Parabolic spectrum
spect_cur = calculate_parabolic_spectra(img);

% Circular spectrum
spe_circ = calculate_circular_spectra(img);

% Plot the spectra
figure;
hold on;
plot(spect_cur, 'LineWidth', 1.5);
plot(spect_lin, 'LineWidth', 1.5);
plot(spe_circ, 'LineWidth', 1.5);
xlabel('Channel');
ylabel('Intensity');
legend('Parabolic Spectrum', 'Linear Spectrum', 'Circular Spectrum');
title(sprintf('Extracted Spectra for %s', files{i}));
grid on;
end

```

7 Results and Discussion

Figure 2: Comparison of RMSE (σ) values for parabolic and circular fits. Lower σ indicates a better fit.

The parabolic and circular models were fitted to the maxima of the captured images, and the RMSE values were compared. The circular fit generally resulted in lower σ values,

indicating a better fit for the experimental data. In contrast, the parabolic fit showed slightly higher σ values, meaning that the circular model was less effective at capturing the curvature of the entrance slit. The result is shown in Figure 2

8 Conclusion

This experiment successfully demonstrated the fitting of parabolic and circular models to the curved entrance slit of a monochromator. The circular model provided a better fit, as evidenced by lower RMSE values than the parabolic models shown in Figure 2. The comparison of the finally obtained spectra from the fitted parameters is shown in Figure 3. Correcting the entrance slit's curvature using the circular fit ensures more accurate wavelength calibration and improved spectral measurements. Future experiments using this spectrometer will benefit from these curvature corrections.

Figure 3: Comparison of spectra obtained with parabolic and circular fits and linear sum.

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Author Contribution

Pratyush Ranjan Sen Sarma (Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4110-3634, email: pratyushranjan.sen-sarma@uva.es): writing original draft, measurements, analysis, and manuscript revision, Maria Teresa Belmonte (0000-0002-3527-201X, email: mariateresa.belmonte@uva.es): funding acquisition, manuscript revision, and conceptualisation. Santiago Mar (Orcid ID:

0000-0003-1988-8129, email: santiago.mar@uva.es): conceptualisation, software, and manuscript revision.